

Software at NASA: Lightning Breakout 1D

ML/AI codes

High performance computing

CHIMAERA System for Cloud Retrievals

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SMD Software Workshop
May 7-9, 2024
Washington, DC

Instrument Interface (CHIMAERA Head)

Input Data Selection

Sensor
Data
Reader

Preparation
for Science
Computation

CHIMAERA Core

Data Format
Abstraction

Memory
Management

General
Purpose
Math
Subroutines

Lookup
Table
Handling

Ancillary
Data
Handling

Pixel-Level Science
Algorithms

Post-Processing Interface (CHIMAERA Tail)

Quality Assurance
Settings

Final Output

ITI: An Instrument-to-instrument Translation tool for Heliophysics and Earth Science

TRILLIUM Δ PLIED

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ITI: An Instrument-to-instrument Translation tool for Heliophysics and Earth Science

Architecture

Jarolim et al.; under review

Unpaired image translation
(no temporal/spatial overlap)

Competitive learning with two
neural networks (GAN)

Framework

Heliophysics use-cases

Earth Science use-cases

High Resolution Earth Atmospheric Predictions using Machine Learning

Presenting: Shannon Bull , NASA GSFC

Dr. Bethany Theiling, NASA GSFC

James MacKinnon, NASA GSFC

Ethan Haengel, NASA GSFC

Contact

Data Sources

Orbiting Carbon Observatory (OCO-2)

OCO-2 Satellite (source: nasa.gov)

Higher coverage

Lower resolution

OCO-2 ground track (source: nasa.gov)

National Ecological Observatory Network (NEON)

NEON tower (source: nsf.gov)

Higher cadence and
Higher resolution

Extremely local

NEON site map (source: nsf.gov)

Data Preparation

More generic

Use OCO-2 spectral data to predict carbon isotopes on the ground

Model architecture: multipath neural network with dense and convolutional layers

Achieved highest accuracy for site-specific models

Future Uses

Prediction algorithms can detect and communicate science anomalies to spacecraft in DSM

Building a foundation model (FM) using Solar Dynamics Observatory (SDO) data: SDO-FM

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Google Cloud

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SDO-FM: A Multi-Modal Foundation Model POC for SDO

Foundation Model Cookbook: Creating co-learning between science and engineering

Milestone 1

Milestone 2

Milestone 3

Apr (15-19) (22-26) (29 Apr - 3 May) May (6-10) (13-17) (20 - 24) (27-31) June (3-7) (10-14) (17-21) (24-28) July (1-5) (8-12) (15-19) (22-26)

Validation Tasks

Identified by science advisory

- Autocalibration
- Recreate Virtual EVE
- Generative EVE

Investigating architectures

Governance Questions

Data pipeline construction

COMPUTE (TPUs) SET-UP

Compute review

Evaluation & Iteration

Recipes

Architectural & Governance Reviews
Recipe Proposals

Technical Memo

- Comparison with primary accuracy
- Scale estimation
- Define future validation tasks

Packaging Stage

Release Documentation & Recipes

Storytelling

DEMO! Governance Recommendations

Governance Plan

SCIENCE & GOVERNANCE Meeting 5th - 6th June

Using Long-Short Term Memory Models to Predict Solar Active Regions Emergence

Towards Discoverability and Cataloging of Rare Class Signals from Large Earth and Space Science Datasets Using Machine Learning

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<https://zenodo.org/records/11117463>

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Signals of interest:

buried in large (dimension, volumes) of multispectral satellite data (**background**)
rare compared to background, **anomalous** given the background

Multispectral Earth,
Space Science data

Reconstruction error-based Inference
high: **anomalous/interesting**
low: **expected**

SME domain
knowledge

Domain specific
datasets

Results (domain adaptive): Earth Science (VIIRS), Heliophysics (SDO/AIA)

Nighttime fires

Gas Flares

SDO (true solar emission)

Ongoing Work:

- Earth science: validation
- Heliophysics: model improvement
- PyPI package

Evaluating Machine Learning Approaches to Plume Tracking

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Overview

The Hunga Tonga-Hunga Ha'apai volcanic eruption on January 15, 2022 exploded a plume of gases, water vapor, and dust through the troposphere into the stratosphere. Prior studies have manually tracked and mapped the plume's impact across the planet. Leveraging open data from NASA's Earth System Observatory, open-source code from NASA's DAACs and OpenScapes program, and open-source machine learning models from Meta, this project explores a synergized approach, and demonstrates an automated, open science methodology for tracking and mapping the Hunga Tonga plume. Furthermore, this project shows how machine learning models can rapidly analyze remote sensing data to help address disasters and accelerate atmospheric research.

Zero-Shot Predictions of the SO₂ Trace Gas Plume

Daily Histograms of SO₂ Input Images

So₂ Input Images

So₂ Feature Masks

Input images are 8bit raster files that have been normalized and scaled from 1-255. Pixels without retrievals due to cloud cover or orbital paths are stored as 0s and illustrated in the darkest shades. Brighter pixels represent higher detected concentrations of SO₂. The feature masks accurately predict plume locations as bright values against dark backgrounds on January 16 and 18.

Methodology

Results

- The Segment Anything model better predicted the location of the sulfur dioxide trace gas plume than aerosol optical depth retrievals or the combined plumes due to noise in input images.
- The model performed best on images with high contrast between the plume and background scene, especially when the input pixels were spatially clustered. The input images on January 16, and January 18 show distinct plumes and high-quality feature masks for locating the plume over time.
- Increasing the number of input coordinates generally reduced accuracy because the pipeline selects pixels based on brightness values, potentially introducing coordinates outside of the plume.
- Open-source tools, like *leafmap* and *folium*, can help researchers create interactive and accessible maps that overlay inputs, masks, and ground retrievals from Aeronet to help with disaster tracking.

Future Work and Applications

- Model performance depends on the availability and quality of the input data. Going forward, this project aims to integrate additional datasets and preprocessing techniques to enhance accuracy.
- Adding CALIPSO Lidar data would add a vertical dimension and could improve the process for identifying input coordinates. Incorporating higher resolution datasets like TROPOMI, or future synergy datasets like the GEO-LEO aerosol products might make aerosol retrievals more useable for machine learning modeling by improving spatial and temporal coverage.
- Exploring spatial clustering of the brightest pixels could help generalize filtering and selecting input points for the model to delineate a shifting plume object across multiple images.
- We hope to evaluate how this approach, codebase, and model can be adapted to study other disasters and extreme events including additional volcanic eruptions and large-scale wildfires such as the 2020 California/Oregon wildfires.

References

- [1] A. Kirillov et al., "Segment Anything," arXiv preprint arXiv:2304.02643, 2023.
- [2] W. Wu et al., "samgeo: A Python package for segmenting geospatial data with the Segment Anything Model (SAM)," *Journal of Open Source Software*, vol. 8, no. 89, p. 5663, 2023, doi: 10.21105/joss.05663.
- [3] Boichu, M., "Growth and Global Persistence of Stratospheric Sulfate Aerosols from the 2022 Hunga Tonga-Hunga Ha'apai Volcanic Eruption," *Journal of Geophysical Research (Atmospheres)*, vol. 128, no. 23, 2023, doi:10.1029/2023J003910.

Data & Model Selection

- MODIS/Aqua Aerosol Cloud Water Vapor Ozone Daily L3 provides gridded global coverage of aerosol optical depth (AOD).
- OMI/Aura Sulfur Dioxide Daily L3 products shows global gridded Total Column Density of SO₂.
- Segment Anything Model (SAM) from Meta takes points in a scene as input and returns feature masks showing the boundaries of an object. This model helps predict and map the plume's location.

Enabling a Queryable Earth

Users Want Answers

"What regions are most vulnerable to air pollution?"

"How can we optimize irrigation systems to conserve water while maximizing yield?"

"What are the patterns of urban sprawl, and how do they affect sustainability?"

"How can we predict flood zones more accurately to enhance emergency response?"

Your Data Has Answers

INSTAGRAM VS REALITY

Applying AI/ML to Geospatial

Searching Your Knowledge Base

Natural Language Geocoding

Natural Language Discovery

Image Embeddings for Search

Image Models

Geospatial Code

Bringing It All Together

What dataset should I use for ...?

...Sentinel level 2 items over the Senegal coastline with less than 20% cloud coverage in 2021

Show me algae within 2 km of the coast of the Cape Cod

Show me areas in West Virginia where there is deforestation in the last year.

Can you show us how to analyze crop health in Sentinel data using Python?